

LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY IN POST-REHABILITATION EXERCISE CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The field of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision presents significant opportunities to advance physical rehabilitation. However, their application in rehabilitation assessment remains underexplored. This study addresses the need for accessible and precise real-time evaluation of post-rehabilitation exercises, contributing to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-Being. The proposed system integrates BlazePose, a human pose estimation model, alongside a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to classify movement correctness and provide real-time feedback. The system was trained on three low back pain rehabilitation exercises from the KinesioTherapy and Rehabilitation for Assisted Ambient Living (KERAAL) dataset. The researchers found that a 13-keypoint skeletal configuration yielded the most optimal performance, achieving an F1-Score of 80% for flank stretch, 78% for torso rotation, and 77% for hiding face. Furthermore, with the same skeletal keypoint configuration and multiple independent training sessions, a Repeated Measures One-Way ANOVA confirmed statistically significant differences ($p < .05$) in F1-Scores across exercises, indicating varied model performance among the exercise types.

COMPUTER SCIENCE CONCEPTS

- Recurrent Neural Network
- Human Pose Estimation
- Deep Learning
- Supervised Learning
- Multilabel Classification

KEYWORDS

LSTM, Human Pose Estimation, BlazePose, Physical Rehabilitation, Motion Analysis, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, Accuracy, Real-time Feedback, Computer Vision, Deep Neural Networks, Artificial Intelligence

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1 INTRODUCTION

The recent surge in the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision in various fields has led to a plethora of new and innovative applications, including human pose estimation, motion analysis, and activity recognition. One such application with great potential for improving the medical field is comparative human motion analysis, which involves comparing body movements to a standard reference for assessment reasons. However, it remains underexplored within the context of computer vision despite the promise it holds for rehabilitation assessment automation in physical rehabilitation.^[1]

Physical rehabilitation plays a critical role in restoring the physical capabilities of an individual after injury, surgery, or illness, with an emphasis on regaining mobility and independence in daily activities.^[2] Despite this, rehabilitation faces its own set of challenges as it often requires medical supervision to ensure proper form and execution during exercise. Additionally, geographical and financial constraints, alongside other limitations, prevent some individuals from accessing regular follow-up care, hindering their ability to achieve full recovery. This study aligns itself with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UNSDG) 3: Good Health and Well-Being^[3], as it aims to make quality rehabilitation more accessible to patients, especially those with limited resources at their disposal, by providing them with a tool to assess and evaluate their rehabilitation exercises during their post-rehabilitation treatment, regardless of location.

In recent years, the utilization of AI, specifically human pose estimation (HPE), has shown great potential in enhancing accuracy in rehabilitation assessments. HPE utilizes whole-body keypoint detection, which entails identifying and tracking keypoints on the body, and is used to monitor rehabilitation exercises using cameras or wearable sensors^{[4][5]}. Moreover, there are implementations of smartphone applications that offer real-time tracking of range of motion (ROM) and joint angles, opening new possibilities for musculoskeletal disorder assessments^{[6][7]}. However, despite these advancements, many of these existing systems do not effectively focus on the most relevant features, such as

prioritizing specific keypoints on the body during the execution of different exercises. This limitation reduces assessment accuracy and prevents the system from providing targeted feedback. Moreover, there remains a significant gap in systems that provide patients with real-time feedback on their rehabilitation exercise execution.

This study aims to address the limitations through a system that utilizes a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model trained on BlazePose keypoints to classify exercise correctness in three lower back rehabilitation exercises. Specifically, the study seeks to determine whether varying keypoint configurations (six, eight, 11, 13, and 15 keypoints) produce significant differences in model performance as measured by Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR), as well as identify differences in Precision, Recall, and F1-Score across the hiding face, torso rotation, and flank stretch exercises. LSTM, a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), is a deep-learning model that is well-suited for analyzing sequential data, making it ideal for modeling and classifying human motion over a set period of time^[8]. For skeletal keypoint extraction, the system employs BlazePose, a lightweight pose estimation model known for its performance and accuracy^[9]. By leveraging the ability of LSTM to capture long-term dependencies, the proposed system aims to deliver an accurate, real-time solution for evaluating rehabilitation exercises. This approach ensures that the system provides feedback to patients, making it a powerful and accessible tool for enhancing the area of physical rehabilitation.

1.1 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on the viability of developing an exercise assessment system for physical rehabilitation, specifically targeting musculoskeletal post-rehabilitation therapy for patients, using an LSTM model to evaluate the extracted motions and classify them based on the correctness of the execution.

The study focuses on exercise data curated from the Kinesiotherapy and Rehabilitation for Assisted Ambient Living (KERAAL) rehabilitation movement dataset, a professionally curated and publicly available dataset repository, which contains three exercises intended for patients with low back pain, providing them with corrective feedback on the execution of their movements.

Several data configurations, specifically on the number of skeletal keypoints used as input features, were tested during model training. Model performance is assessed using Repeated Measures One-Way ANOVA to ensure reliability and generalizability of the model in evaluating the correctness of the exercise execution among the three exercise types.

2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter details the methodologies applied in the study, covering the research design, datasets, procedures, measurement tools, data analysis, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations. The methods were designed to support the goal of developing an application for post-rehabilitation exercise evaluation. This systematic approach ensures accuracy, consistency, and reliability in data collection, processing, and analysis.

2.1 Research Design

The study employed a quantitative approach to evaluate model performance, utilizing accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-Score. Several training, validation, and testing iterations were performed by varying the global seed to ensure reliable and consistent results. The methodology integrates BlazePose for human pose estimation and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for classifying rehabilitation exercise execution. This systematic approach ensures the accuracy, reliability, and generalizability of the findings of the study.

2.2 Dataset

The study utilized the professionally curated and publicly available Kinesiotherapy and Rehabilitation for Assisted Ambient Living (KERAAL) dataset, consisting of 2,622 data points. Preprocessing steps involved removing samples lacking skeletal keypoint data and refining annotations. Additional annotation was performed by a licensed physical therapist to ensure labeling accuracy for exercise execution errors, affected body parts, and accurate timestamp recording, as not all data points were completely annotated. The dataset included five different directories, all containing skeletal keypoint data of the various exercise execution data categorized by patient and volunteer samples. The dataset underwent one-hot encoding to convert categorical labels into numerical form for deep learning input. Finally, the dataset was split into train (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) sets to ensure model generalization and performance evaluation.

Samples lacking skeletal keypoint data from their BlazePose JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) files were excluded, while the remaining data were refined through annotation and restructuring. A licensed physical therapist annotated Groups 1B and 2B, labeling each exercise execution with corresponding error types, affected body parts, and timestamps to ensure consistency and reliability. The finalized and organized dataset was then prepared for model training and testing. The overall process is illustrated in Figure 1, which presents the dataset preprocessing workflow.

Figure 1. Dataset Preprocessing Workflow.

2.3 Procedures

The development of the post-rehabilitation exercise classification system involved several stages, including data processing, model training, and evaluation. Video data were converted into 3D skeletal keypoints using BlazePose, producing labeled coordinates for each exercise execution. These data were then used to train an LSTM model, with random undersampling applied to address class imbalance between correct and incorrect movements. Model performance was optimized through hyperparameter tuning, adjusting parameters such as learning rate, batch size, and epochs to improve accuracy and generalization. The resulting system effectively classifies post-rehabilitation exercises for real-world application.

2.3 Measurement and Statistical Treatment

The study evaluates model performance using four key metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-Score. These metrics collectively assess the ability of the LSTM model to classify post-rehabilitation exercise execution. Each metric provides a specific insight into the predictive behavior and overall reliability of the model.

Accuracy measures the overall performance of the model by weighing all classes equally. It is calculated as the number of correct predictions over the total number of predictions. This metric, as seen in Formula 1, provides the overall percentage of correctly classified samples across all classes.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Formula 1. Accuracy.

However, accuracy alone is misleading in cases of class imbalance, as it does not reflect how well the model performs on specific classes and skews the results towards the majority class.

Precision measures how accurately the model identifies positive predictions among all instances predicted as positive. This ensures that the model correctly classifies

true positives while minimizing false positive results, as calculated in Formula 2.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Formula 2. Precision.

A higher precision value indicates that the model is reliable in identifying correctly executed exercises and avoiding misclassifications.

Recall measures the ability of the model to correctly identify all relevant positive instances in the dataset. It is computed using the equation in Formula 3. This metric determines how well the model captures all correct exercises without missing any true positives.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Formula 3. Recall.

A higher recall indicates fewer missed detections of correctly executed exercises and a more sensitive classification system.

F1-Score balances both precision and recall to provide a comprehensive measure of model performance. It is expressed as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, as shown in Formula 4. This score provides an overall evaluation of the ability of the model to balance false positives and false negatives.

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Formula 4. F1-Score.

A higher F1-Score signifies a more reliable and consistent classification system for exercise evaluation, making it an essential metric in model assessment.

2.4 Area Under the Precision Recall (AUC-PR) Curve

This performance metric summarizes the trade-off between precision and recall across all possible classification thresholds. This metric is particularly well-suited for evaluation on models trained on imbalanced datasets. As this study exhibits a noticeable imbalance

within the data samples, wherein a significant number of negative (correct) examples greatly exceeds that of the positive (incorrect) examples, use of AUC-PR provides a more reliable and informative performance measure than conventional metrics such as accuracy or Area Under the Curve – Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUC-ROC).

To solve for the Precision-Recall (PR) Curve, the precision and recall values are plotted against each other for a range of decision thresholds applied to the probabilistic output of the model. Afterwards, the AUC-PR then quantifies how well the model distinguishes between correct and incorrect movements over all thresholds. The AUC-PR is mathematically defined as the integral of the precision-recall curve over all recall values, where $P(R)$ denotes precision as a function of recall R . This integral is approximated numerically using the trapezoidal rule, based on discrete precision and recall values computed from the output probabilities of the model. Consequently, a higher AUC-PR value indicates that the model effectively balances precision and recall while demonstrating effective performance under class imbalance.

2.5 Bootstrapping

To determine whether a statistically significant difference exists between the classification performance of the model on the three exercises, a bootstrap significance test was applied. This resampling-based method estimates the variability of performance metrics to assess if observed differences between exercises are genuine or due to random chance.

The procedure involves repeatedly computing evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-Score across thousands of resampled datasets. For each iteration, the difference in performance between the two exercises is calculated using Formula 5.

$$D_i = \text{Metric}A_i - \text{Metric}B_i$$

Formula 5. Difference Between Exercises.

where A_i and B_i are the metric scores for the two exercises. After generating the distribution of differences, a 95% confidence interval is computed using Formula 6.

$$CI_{95\%} = [P_{2.5}(D), P_{97.5}(D)]$$

Formula 6. Confidence Interval.

If the interval includes zero, the difference is not statistically significant. Otherwise, if it does not include zero, then it is statistically significant.

2.6 Repeated Measures One-Way Analysis of Variance

A Repeated Measures One-Way ANOVA was used to evaluate whether significant differences existed between the performance of the model across the three exercises. This test was chosen over a standard one-way ANOVA since the same trained model instance was measured multiple times. The main computation for repeated measures one-way ANOVA is illustrated in Formula 7.

$$F = \frac{MSS_b}{MSS_w}$$

Formula 7. Repeated Measures ANOVA.

To compute this, the variation between exercises was calculated using the sum of squares between conditions, as shown in Formula 8. This value measures the mean performance difference between each exercise type. A higher value shows greater variability among group means.

$$SS_b = n \times \sum (\bar{X}_g - \bar{X}_o)^2$$

Formula 8. Sum of Squares Between Conditions.

The degrees of freedom for the conditions were also calculated to obtain independent information about the variability between exercises, as shown in Formula 9. This value helps determine the number of independent comparisons made in the analysis.

$$df_b = k - 1$$

Formula 9. Degree of Freedom for Conditions.

Unlike the standard ANOVA, the repeated measures design also accounts for variability between subjects. This value, shown in Formula 10, represents random variation between the five independent training runs and removes this component from the error term.

$$SS_w = SS_{total} - SS_b - SS_{subjects}$$

Formula 10. Sum of Squares for Errors.

Finally, the degrees of freedom for error were computed to calculate the mean square error, as shown in Formula 11. This ensures the test accurately evaluates variation between conditions relative to residual variation within the model results.

$$df_w = (n - 1) \times (k - 1)$$

Formula 11. Degree of Freedom for Errors.

To ensure reliability, five independent training runs were performed for the champion model configuration, each initialized with a different random seed while keeping other parameters constant. Each model instance was tested on all three exercises, forming the paired data required for repeated measures ANOVA. If a significant result was found, Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc tests were applied to determine which exercises significantly differed in performance.

3 RESULTS

The results were gathered using distributions of exercise types and errors in splits totaling 2,339 data points. Each skeletal keypoint execution is identified correctly if it is labeled as zero (0); otherwise, it is labeled as one (1) for incorrect skeletal keypoint execution. The model is trained for a total of 150 epochs, with callback procedures that allow for early stopping and the ability to restore the model to its best-performing weights based on the selected metric. In this case, the proponents opted to save based on the F1-Score performance of the model. The results are based on metrics such as the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-Score of the model, giving precision, recall, and F1-Score higher importance. Among the 10 experimentation sessions, the 13th training session provided the most optimal results.

3.1 Different Skeletal Keypoints AUC-PR

Feature engineering is an important aspect in deep learning as it helps deep learning models learn patterns more effectively and efficiently. To identify the optimal number of skeletal keypoints as input features, the experiments were conducted across five configurations, each using a different number of skeletal keypoints from BlazePose as input to the LSTM model. These configurations consisted of six, eight, 11, 13, and 15 keypoints. To obtain a statistically robust estimate of the performance of the model for each configuration, bootstrapping was employed for 1,000 iterations to compute the macro-averaged AUC-PR. Bootstrapping

was used as the model was trained under a fixed seed and configuration setup, and no multiple independent training sessions were performed. This resampling approach enables a rigorous assessment of performance variability and generalization stability without the need for additional model training.

Among the various configurations, the 13-keypoint setup achieved the highest mean AUC-PR of around 0.86, indicating superior precision-recall trade-offs compared to other configurations. This suggests that the inclusion of facial features such as the nose and eyes provided additional discriminative motion cues for the LSTM model. Figure 2 illustrates the macro-averaged AUC-PR score distribution across 1,000 bootstrapped iterations

Figure 2. Macro-Averaged AUC-PR Distribution.

For comparison, Table 1 summarizes the corresponding macro-averaged F1-Scores for each configuration and exercise type. The 13-keypoint configuration consistently outperformed the other configurations, achieving F1-Scores of 78% for hiding face, 78% for torso rotation, and 90% for flank stretch. There is a noticeable decline in performance as more skeletal keypoints are added as input features. A negative marginal return is observed with the addition of the skeletal keypoints of the mouth. These results further support that the 13-keypoint setup offers the most effective balance between skeletal detail and classification.

Number of Skeletal Keypoints	Hiding Face	Torso Rotation	Flank Stretch
Six	73 %	76 %	87 %
Eight	74 %	76 %	87 %
Ten	74 %	76 %	89 %
Thirteen	78 %	78 %	90 %
Fifteen	74 %	78 %	89 %

Table 1. Macro Average F1-Score.

3.2 Repeated Measures One-Way ANOVA Performance Metric Results

To determine if the performance of the champion model varied significantly across the different exercises, a repeated-measure one-way ANOVA was conducted, as the experimental design involved testing the same five independently trained model instances across the three exercise types. This approach accounts for the relatedness of the measurements. The key performance metrics analyzed were the macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1-Score.

Table 2 illustrates the repeated measures ANOVA results for the macro precision metric. The analysis yielded a large F-ratio of 328.34 with a p-value of $< .001$. As this falls well below the significance threshold of $p < 0.05$, these findings confirm that a statistically significant difference in precision exists among the three exercise classes.

One-Way ANOVA Precision				
Source	SS	df	MS	Source
Between-treatments	0.1029	2	0.0514	$F = 328.34043$
Within-treatments	0.0027	12	0.0002	
Error	0.0013	8	0.0002	
The f -ratio value is 328.34043. The p -value is .0001. The result is significant at $p < .05$.				

Table 2. One-Way ANOVA Precision.

Given the significant result from the repeated measures ANOVA for the recall metric, Bonferroni-corrected pairwise post-hoc tests^[10] were conducted to identify which specific exercise groups differed significantly from each other. This analysis involves performing a series of paired t-tests and adjusting the resulting p-values to control for multiple comparisons. The results are then compared to a threshold to identify if there is a significant difference between the components being compared. The comparison between hiding face, with a mean of 0.704, and torso rotation, with a mean of 0.732, shows a mean difference of -0.028. This result yields a t-statistic of $t(4) = -3.50$, corresponding to an uncorrected p-value of 0.0248.

After applying the Bonferroni correction, the adjusted p-value is 0.0744, which is not statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level. The comparison between hiding face, with a mean of 0.704, and flank stretch, with a mean of 0.890,

reveals a large mean difference of -0.186. This results in a t-statistic of $t(4) = -18.98$, with a corrected p-value of $< .001$, indicating a highly statistically significant difference. Lastly, the comparison between torso rotation, with a mean of 0.732, and flank stretch, with a mean of 0.890, shows a mean difference of -0.158. This yields a t-statistic of $t(4) = -19.75$, with a corrected p-value of $< .001$, which is also highly statistically significant. These results indicate that while the precision of the model for hiding face and torso rotation is statistically similar, both are significantly lower than its precision for the flank stretch exercise. The detailed results are presented in Table 3.

Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparisons for Precision (Bonferroni)			
Comparison	Mean Difference	T-statistic (df=4)	p-correlation
hiding face vs torso rotation	-0.028	-3.50	.074
hiding face vs flank stretch	-0.186	-18.98	$< .001$
torso rotation vs flank stretch	-0.158	-19.75	$< .001$

Table 3. Post-Hoc Bonferroni Precision.

Next, Table 4 presents the repeated measures ANOVA results for the recall metric. The analysis yielded a large F-ratio of 22.39033 with a p-value of 0.000528, which falls well below the significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. These findings confirm that a statistically significant difference in recall exists among the three exercise classes.

One-Way ANOVA Recall				
Source	SS	df	MS	Source
Between-treatments	0.0432	2	0.0216	$F = 22.39033$
Within-treatments	0.0124	12	0.001	
Error	0.0077	8	0.001	
The f -ratio value is 328.34043. The p -value is .000528. The result is significant at $p < .05$.				

Table 4. One-Way ANOVA Recall.

With the recall metric ANOVA result, Bonferroni-corrected pairwise post-hoc tests were performed to determine which exercise groups significantly differed from each other. The comparison between hiding face,

with a mean recall of 0.792, and torso rotation, with a mean of 0.830, yielded a corrected p-value of 0.052, which does not meet the threshold for statistical significance.

However, the comparison between hiding face and flank stretch, with a mean of 0.902, revealed a highly significant difference of $p < .001$. Similarly, the difference between torso rotation and flank stretch was also found to be statistically significant with $p = .002$. This indicates that the ability of the model to recall errors was significantly better for flank stretch than for the other exercises.

Table 5 illustrates the significant difference that flank stretch has in terms of its recall among the three exercises, indicating the model performs better when flank stretch is performed, and supports the notion that the model performs well in identifying true positives, specifically, incorrectly executed motions.

Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparisons for Recall (Bonferroni)			
Comparison	Mean Difference	T-statistic (df=4)	p-correlation
hiding face vs torso rotation	-0.038	-3.92	.052
hiding face vs flank stretch	-0.110	-17.39	< .001
torso rotation vs flank stretch	-0.072	-9.00	.002

Table 5. Post-Hoc Bonferroni Recall.

Lastly, Table 6 presents the repeated measures ANOVA results for the F1-Score metric across the three exercise classes. With a large F-ratio of 56.39 and a p-value of < .001, the analysis confirmed that there is a highly significant difference in F1-Score among the exercises, indicating varied performance of the model on this comprehensive metric.

One-Way ANOVA F1-Score				
Source	SS	df	MS	Source
Between-treatments	0.0778	2	0.0389	$F = 56.38647$
Within-treatments	0.01	12	0.0008	
Error	0.0055	8	0.0007	

The f -ratio value is 56.38647. The p -value is .000019. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Table 6. One-Way ANOVA F1-Score.

Given the significant ANOVA result for F1-Score, Bonferroni-corrected pairwise post-hoc tests were performed to determine which exercise groups significantly differed from each other, as shown in Table 7. The comparison between hiding face, with a mean of 0.742, and torso rotation, with a mean of 0.776, resulted in a corrected p-value of 0.016, which is statistically significant. The analysis also revealed a highly significant difference between both hiding face and flank stretch with $p < .001$, and torso rotation and flank stretch with $p < .001$. These results demonstrate a clear performance hierarchy, with flank stretch achieving the highest F1-Scores, followed by torso rotation, and finally hiding face, with all pairwise differences being statistically significant. This indicates that the ability of the model to balance precision and recall varies substantially across exercise types, reflecting differences in movement complexity and keypoint engagement. Moreover, the consistent superiority of flank stretch suggests that its motion patterns are more distinctly captured by the selected skeletal configuration, leading to more reliable classification performance.

Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparisons for F1-Score (Bonferroni)			
Comparison	Mean Difference	T-statistic (df=4)	p-correlation
hiding face vs torso rotation	-0.034	-5.49	.016
hiding face vs flank stretch	-0.150	-26.07	< .001
torso rotation vs flank stretch	-0.116	0	< .001

Table 7. Post-Hoc Bonferroni F1-Score.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion and recommendations of the research paper present the solutions to the problem statements and discuss the potential improvements to the study. Moreover, this section also provides a summary of the results obtained throughout the experimentation process. This section intends to present the overall summary of the research and its findings.

4.1 Conclusion

There are two problem statements that the researchers aimed to answer. Each section talks about the steps performed, results, and conclusions attained by the

researchers. Particularly, it discusses the skeletal keypoints that comprise the model that yielded the best results, the performance metrics, and the training session of the model.

4.1.1 Skeletal Keypoint. The model underwent training for a maximum of 150 epochs using early stopping, with batches of 32 samples and a 70-15-15 split for training, validation, and testing data. Each epoch required roughly 5 minutes, resulting in typical training sessions of about 6 hours and 32 minutes per model. Results of the macro-average AUC-PR distribution showed that performance generally increased as more keypoints were added, suggesting that additional spatial information about patient positioning benefits the LSTM model. However, this trend was not linear, and the performance decreased when all 15 skeletal keypoints were used. This demonstrates the principle of diminishing returns in feature engineering for this specific model architecture.

The most substantial and statistically significant improvement came from adding hip keypoints in the 8-keypoint model, which boosted performance with a mean difference of +0.0415 and $p < .001$ over the 6-keypoint baseline. While additional keypoints continued to enhance performance beyond the baseline, the incremental gains varied. The best results were achieved using 13 keypoints consisting of both eyes, both ears, both shoulders, both elbows, both wrists, both hips, and the nose.

Crucially, expanding to 15 keypoints resulted in a significant decline in model performance compared to the optimal 13-keypoint model, with a mean decrease of -0.0220 and $p < .001$. This confirms that past a certain threshold, additional features contribute more noise than valuable information, causing the model to overfit to irrelevant details or making the feature space too complex for the architecture to handle effectively. This phenomenon highlights the importance of methodical feature selection rather than assuming more data is always better.

Based on this comprehensive statistical evaluation, the 13-keypoint model was identified as the champion configuration. It provided the highest mean AUC-PR and demonstrated a statistically significant advantage over all other configurations.

4.1.2 Per Exercise Performance Metrics Analysis. Statistical testing using repeated measures one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc comparisons provided a clear response to the research question regarding how well the optimal model performs across three different rehabilitation exercises. The findings consistently showed that the error classification accuracy of the model varies significantly between

movements, revealing a distinct performance hierarchy among the exercises.

The flank stretch exercise consistently emerged as the model that performed best, recording the highest average scores for precision, recall, and F1-Score. Post-hoc analysis confirmed that its performance significantly exceeded both hiding face and torso rotation across nearly all three metrics. It suggested that error patterns in this exercise are most distinctive and easily identified by the LSTM model. This performance is likely due to the side-bending movement being relatively planar and having minimal obstruction.

In contrast, the hiding face exercise proved to be the most difficult for the model. It consistently produced the lowest average precision and F1-Scores. Although its recall was similar to torso rotation, its significantly lower precision indicates that the model frequently made errors in evaluating this exercise. This difficulty is due to the complexities of the movement, including self-occlusion of keypoints as the arms and hands move toward the face, and the subtle nature of common errors like shoulder shrugging.

The torso rotation exercise showed moderate performance levels. Statistical analysis revealed that its F1-Score and precision were superior to hiding face but significantly lower than the flank stretch. This suggests that while rotational movement provides clearer error signals than hiding face, it presents greater classification challenges than flank stretch.

In summary, the data strongly support the hypothesis that model performance differs significantly across exercises. The clear performance hierarchy of flank stretch, followed by torso rotation, and lastly hiding face, is statistically robust. This finding underscores the importance of exercise-specific evaluation and highlights that the effectiveness of a pose-based error detection system is highly dependent on the biomechanical characteristics and potential for occlusion within the specific movements being analyzed.

4.2 Recommendations

The results of this research provided significant improvements over baseline performance by creating a unified deep learning model that combines motion detection and error classification for real-time rehabilitation feedback. However, several limitations were identified that present opportunities for future research.

Minor overfitting observed during training suggests the dataset is too small for the LSTM architecture. LSTM models require substantial and diverse data to generalize properly and to prevent the model from memorizing training patterns. To reduce overfitting and improve the

reliability, generalization, and overall performance of the model, particularly for exercises involving movement differences, expansion of the dataset with varied samples of correct and incorrect movements across different subjects is advised.

Since most dataset frames contain no keypoint-level errors, refining the preprocessing stage is recommended. Implementing a preprocessing strategy that identifies where keypoint-specific errors commonly occur in each exercise allows for the removal of non-informative sequences that do not contribute to the learning of incorrect motion patterns. By focusing on sequences with at least one keypoint-level error, the model trains on more relevant data, thus improving its error detection sensitivity while addressing class imbalance. This error-centric filtering data pruning technique promotes enhance localization accuracy and error-class recall.

Lastly, exhaustive hyperparameter exploration during experimentation was not employed to avoid overfitting to hyperparameters and maintain experimental consistency. A more systematic hyperparameter tuning approach is recommended to achieve a near-optimal model configuration. Further studies are advised to employ efficient search methods such as Bayesian optimization or random search with successive halving. The optimization of hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size, regularization, and dropout rates holds potential for significant performance improvements.

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